

Scutellarein-4'-L-arabinoside from the leaves of *Clerodendron nerifolium*

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In view of the recent interest in the study of flavonoid patterns in plants belonging to the natural order Tubiflorae containing the rare 6-hydroxy flavones¹ and flavone uronides² and the report on the isolation of acacetin-7-glucuro-glucoronide from *Clerodendron trichotomum*³, we have examined the leaves of *C. nerifolium* (Verbenaceae) and the results are recorded below in brief.

Fresh leaves of *Clerodendron nerifolium*, collected from our Institute campus were extracted and fractionated in the usual way. The yellow solid from ether concentrate on recrystallisation from MeOH yielded a flavone (0.15%) as bright yellow needles, λ_{max} . 286, 329 nm, not melting below 320°. It gave typical colour reactions of a 5,6,7-trihydroxy system and yielded a tetraacetate, m.p. and m.m.p. 236°–38°. It was identified as scutellarein (4',5,6,7-tetrahydroxy flavone) and the identity confirmed by co- R_f and direct comparison with an authentic sample⁴. The ether mother liquor on paper chromatography showed the presence of traces of acacetin (4'-methyl apigenin) and hispidulin (6-methyl scutellarein).

The EtOAc concentrate yielded a small quantity of an yellow solid (0.005%) which was recrystallised from MeOH-Me₂CO to yield light yellow solid, m.p. 204°–05° (decomp.), λ_{max} . 285, 335 (MeOH); 288, 335 (NaOAc) and 303, 366 (AlCl₃) nm. It gave green colour with Fe³⁺, exhibited dull purple-yellow fluorescence and had characteristic colour changes comparable to scutellarein. On acid hydrolysis it yielded scutellarein and L-arabinose. From the colour reactions (suggestive of free hydroxyls at 5, 6 and 7), products of hydrolysis, spectral data and paper chromatography, the glycoside was identified as scutellarein-4'-L-arabinoside.

The EtOAc mother liquor on paper chromatography was found to contain two more flavone glycosides. They were separated by preparative paper chromatography using *n*-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent system (R_f : 0.40 and 0.72). The glycoside from the upper zone (R_f : 0.72) was identified as acacetin-7-glucoside by paper chromatography, λ_{max} . (276, 332 nm) and formation of acacetin and glucose by acid hydrolysis. The glycoside with lower R_f (0.40) was identified as an acacetin glucuronide by the formation of acacetin and glucuronic acid on acid hydrolysis (10% H₂SO₄ in acetic acid medium).

This is the first record of occurrence of scutellarein-4'-L-arabinoside and is the only scutellarein pentoside so far known. The presence of high proportions of free scutellarein with small quantities of its glycoside in *C. nerifolium* is unusual in Tubiflorae² and may be due to the easy hydrolysibility of scutellarein-4'-arabinoside. The occurrence of acacetin and its uronide is earlier recorded in sister species³. Luteolin and apigenin which have been recorded to be common flavones of Verbenaceae⁵ are absent in *C. nerifolium*.

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